

Article

The Hybrid (Virtual / Traditional) Workplace: Changes in the Organization of Work *Autonomy and the Participative Process*

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"The Meaning of Work: Papers on Organization and the Design of Jobs" (2018), acknowledges the increase of autonomy in work and its impact on the participative process to address change in design groups. Furthermore, the premise is that the design groups employing the participative process should be representative of all direct users. However, in new systems, the design groups representative of all direct users, and their experience, do not yet exist (Klein, 2018).

Thus, in new systems, such as the hybrid virtual traditional workplace, changes to the internal environment such as job, work, and business processes, particularly modified standardized processes, may not be implemented because direct users and the participative process of design groups may not yet exist. Also, due to the autonomy in work in the hybrid environment, information simply may not be shared; thereby, not fully accepted (See e.g. Zeller 2017). Overall, people working in the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace may find it difficult to be drawn into a design group and the participative process because they and their experience are to some extent limited or are not yet recognized.

The issue is relevant because "to remain competitive, organizations must continually 'fit' both internal design and structure; in a variety of external environments" (Brewster, Sparrow, & Vernon, 2007; Edwards, 2004; Zeller, 2018). In order to do so, the participative process needs to have the "capacity to anticipate or detect surprises early and without compromising routine operations" (Ericksen & Dyer, 2004, p.11; Zeller, 2019). Then, for the long term, "robust and resilient organizational systems capable of withstanding and responding to the uncertainties and challenges" are required to continually identify, implement, and support change (Bhamra, 2016, p. 4; Zeller, 2019).

Discussion

As the implementation of a hybrid (virtual /traditional) workplace changes where and how work is done; a redesign, reorganization, or an altogether new work system may be needed. In particular, Klein (2018) suggests that when designing a new work system, such as in the hybrid workplace, the people working in it cannot be drawn into the participative process because, by definition, they and their experience do not exist yet.

Since experience with hybrid (virtual / traditional) work, particularly the autonomy thereof, is to some extent limited or may not exist yet, the challenge is how to select design groups and how to create a participative process to identify and implement change.

While there are several scenarios that can develop; for this paper, one will be highlighted. Basically, the organizations included in this Discussion Section have decided to revise a long-standing hybrid work option.

In 2016, Honeywell's decision to ban its policy offering virtual work office privileges for all employees not in sales or field service was announced "at a time of lackluster growth in the global industrial sector and at a time of restructuring" of the large New Jersey-based organization (Depass, 2016; Zeller, Summer 2018; Zeller, Summer 2021). Then, during the pandemic of 2020, Honeywell had to reinstate its work from home policy (Greig, 2021; Zeller, Summer 2021). Currently, Honeywell is evaluating post-pandemic plans for the workforce. Although the organization is reviewing hybrid arrangements, the goal is to get everyone to return to the office (Capgemini, 2021; Zeller, Summer 2021).

Microsoft "has long said it would embrace a hybrid work environment"; however, change appears to be on the horizon. According to a February 28, 2022 announcement, Microsoft employees will be required to return to the corporate offices (Weise, 2022). In this case, the reason is based on the decline in the pandemic cases.

With the hybrid virtual traditional work practices, where and how people work has changed. A major challenge to the recommended participative process in design groups is the changes to work modules, including job design, that create a disconnect between jobs, processes, and structure (Sinha & Van de Ven, 2005; Zeller, 2017). Furthermore, "a number of scholars have recently pointed out that current theoretical models and empirical studies of job design no longer reflect--and have yet to integrate--the impact of the dramatic changes in work contexts that have taken place" (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010, p. 145; Zeller, 2017). Oldham and Hackman's (2010) recommendations to address the mismatch include investigating how organizational contexts and work processes may influence our knowledge of job designs; and to understand the juxtaposition of organizations and job / work / business process designs (Grant, Fried, Parker, & Frese, 2010; Zeller, 2017).

In new systems, such as the hybrid (virtual / traditional) workplace, experience may be limited. Nevertheless, with their knowledge of corporate processes, the existing workforce may be able to provide information such as where change is needed.

In the aforementioned scenarios, Honeywell and Microsoft, the situation has changed again and then again. Hence, the participative process is not static; it is a continually evolving process whereby the design group needs to identify the social networks of the workforce in connection with the organizational processes and the use of technology. That is, in order to fit the problem, the human network interaction; job / work / business processes; technology; and work environment needs to be addressed.

Klein (2005) identifies the challenges and proposes the outcome:

"What the technologists want are 'user models' and 'enterprise models' that automatically embody human and organizational issues so that designers do not need qualifications in social science, and systems can be designed without elaborate organizational research. The challenge for the social scientist is to respond with methods and tools that encourage exploring and learning strategies in technologists and users. The outcome should not be a product that can be applied without understanding, but a process that leads to the development of appropriate understanding" (Klein, 2005, p 189).

Given that "there are likely to be 'working hypotheses' that are jointly explored and may be jointly modified as the work proceeds"; action research is applicable (Klein, 2005, p 185). However, perhaps as a note of precaution, Klein (2005) recognizes that "as regards methods, it is not a matter of intervening in an ad-hoc and uncontrolled way....but of selecting and agreeing on strategies (a) in a way that fits the problem and (b) in knowledge of their consequences, generally documenting them, and staying in role" (p 186).

Conclusion

To remain competitive, organizations must continually 'fit' both internal design and structure with the external environment. Continually aligning the workforce and corporate goals is fundamental to achieving that goal. However, the physical location of work, whether temporary, permanent, or in the midst of change creates a ripple effect of change to internal and external operations throughout the organization. Hence, at the business level, the business, job, and work processes are subject to change. And, at the organizational level, structure, design, and management are likely to change, as well.

Involving the hybrid virtual traditional workforce in active roles to address change aligns with the participative process of design groups; however, the question is whether the people working in it can be drawn into the process because, by definition, they and their experience do not exist yet. In this case, prior or untapped experience of the workforce may be a valid resource; nevertheless, additional resources may be needed to address new requirements.

Then, an action research approach will allow for the situation to be changing while the work is going on. However, Klein (2005) cautions against approaching the issues in an ad-hoc manner. Instead, Klein (2005) proposes methods that include selecting and agreeing on strategies that (a) in a way that fits the problem and (b) in knowledge of their consequences, generally documenting them, and staying in role.

Accordingly, the participative process as well as design groups for the hybrid virtual traditional workplace are likely to change while the work is going on. Overall, it is a moving target that requires strategic, dynamic development of the understanding of job, work, and business processes while continually adapting to where and how people work, at all levels.

References

Bhamra, R. (2016). *Organisational resilience. Concepts, integration and practice*. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press

Brewster, C., Sparrow, P., & Vernon, G. (2007). *International human resource management*, 2nd Ed. London: CIPD

Capgemini (2021). Discussion with Sheila Jordan, Chief Digital and Technology Officer, Honeywell. From <https://www.capgemini.com/us-en/research/conversations-for-tomorrow/conversations-for-tomorrow-2/discussion-with-sheila-jordan-chief-digital-and-technology-officer-honeywell/>

Depass, D. (2016). Honeywell ends telecommuting option. Star Tribune. From <http://m.startribune.com/honeywell-ends-telecommuting-option/397929641/>

Edwards, T. (2004) Transfer of employment practices across borders in multinational companies. *International Human Resource Management*, pp 389-410, London: Sage

Ericksen, J. & Dyer, L. (2004). Toward a strategic human resource management model of high reliability organization performance (CAHRS Working Paper #04-02). Ithaca, NY: Cornell University, School of Industrial and Labor Relations, Center for Advanced Human Resource Studies. From <http://digitalcommons.ilr.cornell.edu/cahrswp/9>

Grant, A.M., Fried, Y., Parker, S.K. & Frese, M. (2010). Introduction: Putting job design in context: Introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31(2/3), 145-157

Greig, (2021). IT leaders from Dell, Honeywell, Vancouver Film School, and City of Amarillo discuss COVID-19 lessons and changes. From

<https://www.zdnet.com/article/it-leaders-from-dell-honeywell-vancouver-film-school-and-city-of-amarillo-discuss-covid-19-lessons-and-changes/>

Klein, Lisl. (2005). Working across the gap: The practice of social science in organizations. London: H. Karnac (Books) Ltd.

Klein, L. (2018). The meaning of work: Papers on work organization and the design of jobs. N.Y.C., N.Y. : Routledge

Sinha, K. & Van de Ven, A. (2005). Designing work within and between organizations. Organization Science, 16(4), 389-408

Weise, K. (2022, Feb). Microsoft tells workers to prepare to return to the office. From

<https://www.nytimes.com/2022/02/14/technology/microsoft-rto.html><https://www.nytimes.com/2022/02/14/technology/microsoft-rto.html>

Zeller, D. (2017). The hybrid work environment: The business process argument for adapting organizational structure. From zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles

Zeller, D. (2017, Fall). The hybrid traditional / virtual workforce: Evolving spatial dimensions and tacit knowledge sharing. From zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles

Zeller, D. (2018, Summer). Organizational design: The hybrid (combined virtual / traditional office) organization. From zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles

Zeller, D. (2018, Fall). Organizational management in the hybrid (combined virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') transnational organizations. From zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles

Zeller, D. (2019, Summer). Strategic human resource management in the hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional 'brick and mortar') organization. From zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles

Zeller, D. (2021, Summer). The hybrid (virtual offsite / traditional office) workplace: Adapting to strategic objectives. From zellerdonna.wixsite.com/books-and-articles